

Entrepreneurship Education and Business Education Students' Social Entrepreneurial Intention Relationship: Does Entrepreneurial Passion Matter?

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Abstract

With rising social problems and graduate unemployment causing unfathomable pain in the country, exploring alternative employment opportunities through business formation that may address societal concerns has become a must. The current study looked at the mediating role of entrepreneurial passion in the relationship between entrepreneurship education and business education students' social entrepreneurial intention in Edo State. Four research questions were posed to lead the investigation. Four hypotheses were developed and tested at the 0.05 level of significance. The study used a correlational survey research approach. The study's population included 382 business education students from the University of Benin and Ambrose Alli University in Ekpoma. A questionnaire termed 'Entrepreneurship Education, Passion and Social Entrepreneurial Intention Questionnaire (EPSEIQ)' was used. Two professionals validated the instrument. After delivering the instrument to 15 business education students at Delta State University, Abraka, Cronbach alpha was used to determine the instrument's reliability, yielding a reliability coefficient of .84. The responses' data were examined using the simple linear regression and SPSS Process Macro analysis. The findings revealed that entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial passion were significant predictors of business education students' social entrepreneurial intention in Edo State. The finding further revealed that entrepreneurial passion significantly mediates the relationship between entrepreneurship education and business education students' social entrepreneurial intention in Edo State. Based on the findings, it was recommended that there should be an urgent need for curriculum revision in higher education institutions to emphasize social entrepreneurship.

Keywords: Business education, entrepreneurial passion, entrepreneurship education, social entrepreneurship, and social entrepreneurial intention

Introduction

Entrepreneurship Education (EE) is a compulsory programme that was introduced into the Nigeria education system as a response to checking the increasing poverty level, unemployment and social vices (Ediagbonya 2022a; 2022b; 2022c). EE as a programme is offered as a compulsory programme across the nation's tertiary institutions. By the design of the programme, it is expected that undergraduates' students will be exposed to both the theoretical and practical components of the programme. The theoretical components are taught just like normal lectures for the learners to appreciate and understand the basics and principles governing entrepreneurship. Institutions often

examine the students based on what they have been taught either via Computer Based Test (CBT) or Paper and Pen Test (PPT) (Ediagbonya, 2023b). The learners are also taught the practical component of the programme which has emphasis on ‘hands-on’. That is, making the learners to put the theories learnt into practice by making products such as paints, shoes, bags, etc. With the exposure of the students to both theory and practical, their mindsets are better repositioned to thinking on how to create wealth via entrepreneurship. This has the tendency of redirecting the students from social vices to productive activities which in turn has a multiplier effect on the economy. Studies by Ediagbonya (2023a), Orah, et al (2013), Agbaje, et al (2013) and Imeokparia and Ediagbonya (2013) have emphasized the significant roles EE plays in the nation’s economic development. Due to the roles played by EE, students are becoming more passionate about launching an entrepreneurial venture. This passion is informed by the students’ exposure the theoretical and practical component of EE.

Entrepreneurial Passion (EP) has continued to attract research interest in the field of entrepreneurship and it has often been studied as one of the antecedents of entrepreneurial intention. EP originates from philosophy and is an individual’s strong tendency toward favourite activities. Baum and Locke (2004) defined EP as individual’s love for entrepreneurial activities based on entrepreneurial background. In this context, entrepreneurial background could mean EE that the individual has been exposed to in their course of study. Cardon and Kirk (2015) believed that EP is the conscious, strong, and positive emotions experienced by entrepreneurs when they participate in entrepreneurial activities. Mueller et al (2017) proposed that EP can enable entrepreneurs to persevere in the face of difficulties and challenges, and further achieve entrepreneurial success. According to Ediagbonya (2023a), EP helps to coordinate cognition and behavior of entrepreneurs, providing the catalyst that propels innovation, persistence, and ultimate success. Entrepreneurial passion enables entrepreneurs to have a stronger sense of identity with the entrepreneurial activities they are engaged in, to be more determined in their entrepreneurial goals, and to be willing to invest more time and material to start a business, to cope with the difficulties and challenges in the process of starting a business and to achieve entrepreneurial success (Hu et al, 2022). Studies have revealed that entrepreneurial passion is closely linked to a whole host of entrepreneurial outcomes, including business formation and performance, access to funding, and entrepreneurial persistence (e.g. Mueller, et al, 2017; Liu, et al, 2021; Schwarte et al, 2023; Ediagbonya, 2023a). It is this EP that propels individuals to venture into social entrepreneurship.

The term ‘social entrepreneur’ was first introduced in 1972 by Banks who noted that social problems could also be solved by managerial practices. Tracey and Phillips (2007) described Social Entrepreneurship (SE) as the entrepreneurship that is concerned with enterprise for social purpose and involves building organizations that have the capacity to be both commercially viable and socially constructive. In a similar vein, SE is described as the utilization of innovation to solve social problems (Sivathanu, & Bhise, 2013; Ruiz-Rosa et al, 2020; Hattab, 2023). Social entrepreneurship is the use of innovative means to create and exploit opportunities that yield sustained solutions to social problems. The emphasis of SE is to launch an entrepreneurial venture

that is capable of addressing the needs of the society (Mohammadi et al, 2020). With the increasing level of hardship, poverty, unemployment, hunger, etc., it becomes important to continue to encourage individuals and corporate bodies to venture into social entrepreneurship. There are so many forces that tend to strengthen people's intent to venture into social entrepreneurship.

Social Entrepreneurial Intention (SEI) is described as an individual's intention to create an innovative business venture that yields sustained solutions to social problems (Zhang et al, 2020). Rozar et al (2020) defined social entrepreneurial intention as the decision made by an entrepreneur to create a new business in creating social changes. Tran and Korflesch (2016) summarized social entrepreneurial intention as a rooted belief, catalyst, desire, determination and engagement for an entrepreneur or a person to assemble a social enterprise. Studies have linked SEI to several antecedents such as passion (Aloulou et al, 2023; Chandra et al, 2023; Ediagbonya, 2023a), entrepreneurship education (Ediagbonya, 2023a), social entrepreneurship self-efficacy (Zhang, et al., 2020) entrepreneurial alertness (Ediagbonya, 2023a); entrepreneurial creativity (Ediagbonya, 2023a). Despite the work done so far in this field, there is still a gap. There is little or no study that has focused on explaining the mediating role of entrepreneurial passion in the relationship between EE and business education students' social entrepreneurial intention in Edo State. This identified gap was filled in this study.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to ascertain the extent to which entrepreneurial passion mediates the relationship between entrepreneurship education and business education students' social entrepreneurial intention in Edo State. Specifically, the study sought to find out:

1. If entrepreneurship education is a significant predictor of business education students' social entrepreneurial intention in Edo State.
2. If entrepreneurship education is a significant predictor of business education students' entrepreneurial passion in Edo State
3. If entrepreneurial passion is a significant predictor of business education students' social entrepreneurial intention in Edo State.
4. If entrepreneurial passion significantly mediates the relationship between entrepreneurship education and business education students' social entrepreneurial intention in Edo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised and answered.

1. Is entrepreneurship education a significant predictor of business education students' social entrepreneurial intention in Edo State?
2. Is entrepreneurship education a significant predictor of business education students' entrepreneurial passion in Edo State?
3. Is entrepreneurial passion a significant predictor of business education students' social entrepreneurial intention in Edo State.?

4. Does entrepreneurial passion significantly mediates the relationship between entrepreneurship education and business education students’ social entrepreneurial intention in Edo State.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study.

1. entrepreneurship education is not a significant predictor of business education students’ social entrepreneurial intention in Edo State.
2. entrepreneurship education is not a significant predictor of business education students’ entrepreneurial passion in Edo State.
3. entrepreneurial passion is not a significant predictor of business education students’ social entrepreneurial intention in Edo State.
4. entrepreneurial passion does not significantly mediates the relationship between entrepreneurship education and business education students’ social entrepreneurial intention in Edo State.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual model on the mediating role of entrepreneurial passion in the entrepreneurship education and social entrepreneurial intention relationship

Figure.1 is a conceptual model that attempts to explain the inter-connections and relationships that exist among the study variables? In this framework, the dependent variable is the social entrepreneurial intention; the independent variable is the entrepreneurship education while the entrepreneurial passion is the mediator. Apart from establishing the relationships among the study variables, this study was specifically designed to see if the EP will significantly mediate the relationship between the EE and SEI.

Method

The design of this study is correlational survey. This design is considered suitable because it has the capacity to determine the relationship that exists among the study variables. The design seeks to establish the extent to which the independent variable (IV) predicts the dependent variable (DV) of social entrepreneurial intention. It also seeks to ascertain the mediating role of entrepreneurial passion. This study's demographic includes all business education students at the University of Benin and the Ambrose Alli University in Ekpoma, Edo State. There were 382 people in total. For the study, the full

population was used. There was no sampling method utilized because the complete population was utilized. A questionnaire was employed for this investigation. The questionnaire was tagged: 'Entrepreneurship Education, Passion and Social Entrepreneurial Intention Questionnaire (EPSEIQ)' and was used to gather information from respondents. It was separated into two sections, A and B. Part A contained the respondents' demographic characteristics such as gender and institution, whereas Part B contained thirteen (13) opinion statements built on a Likert Scale with the response Strongly Agree (SA). Agree (A), Neutral (N), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD) were weighted 5, 4, 3, 2, 1 accordingly. The entrepreneurship education component consisted of three measures derived from Walter and Block (2016). One of the items reads 'My education in school helped me better understand the role of entrepreneurs in society'. Three items taken from Cardon et al. (2013) made up the entrepreneurial passion component. One of the instrument's readings is 'It is exciting to figure out new ways to solve unmet market needs that that can be commercialized'. The Social Entrepreneurial Intention (SEI) component included three items modified from Hockerts (2017). One of the items in the instrument reads 'I expect that at some point in the future, I will be involved in launching an organization that aims to solve social problems'.

The content and face validity of the instrument were tested. It was distributed to vocational education specialists, who provided feedback on the draft instrument, which was included into the final questionnaire. The Cronbach alpha coefficient was .84 after administering the measure to 15 vocational education students at Delta State University, Abraka, Delta State. The researcher collected data online by sending Google form links to Respondents. The researcher was able to obtain 244 questionnaires from the respondents, which amounted to 63.9 percent of the population. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0 was used for the analysis. Hypotheses 1, 2 and 3 were examined using Simple Linear Regression Analysis, and hypothesis 4 was investigated using SPSS Process Macro to ascertain the mediation.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Linear regression estimates of the direct relationship between the study variables

Pathways	Bootstrap with BCa 95% CI								
	SE(β)	F	T	Bias	R ²	AdjR ²	P	Lower Limit	Upper Limit
EE → EP	.026 (.166)	34.488	5.873	.000	.125	.121	.000	.116	.216
EE → SEI	.035	50.892	7.134	.000	.174	.170	.000	.152	.291

	(.220)								
EP → SEI	.074	35.953	5.996	.001	.129	.126	.000	.260	.554
	(.405)								

Note: EE – Entrepreneurship Education; EP – Entrepreneurial Passion; SEI – Social Entrepreneurial Intention; AdjR² – Adjusted R-squared
 Source: Researchers’ Fieldwork, 2024

Table 1 reveals that EE (F (1, 242) = 50, 892, SE = .074, β = .405, t = 7.134, 95% LLCI = .152 – ULCI = .291 had a significant positive influence on SEI. The adjusted R-square (.170) reveals that 17% of the variance in SEI is influenced by EE. The results of the 5000-resample bootstrap coefficients for EE influencing SEI (bias = .000, p = .000) were statistically significant. All in all, the results confirmed the expectations of the authors. Therefore, hypothesis 2 is rejected in the study.

Table 1 reveals that EE (F (1, 242) = 34,488, SE = .026, β = .166, t = 5.873, 95% LLCI = .116 – ULCI = .216 had a significant positive influence on EP. The adjusted R-square (.121) reveals that 12.1% of the variance in EP is influenced by EE. The results of the 5000-resample bootstrap coefficients for EE influencing EP (bias = .000, p = .000) were statistically significant. All in all, the results confirmed the expectations of the authors. Therefore, hypothesis 1 is rejected in the study.

Further analysis also reveals that EP (F (1, 242) = 35, 953, SE = .035, β = .220, t = 5.996, 95% LLCI = .260 – ULCI = .554 had a significant positive influence on SEI. The adjusted R-square (.126) reveals that 12.6% of the variance in SEI is influenced by EP. The results of the 5000-resample bootstrap coefficients for EP influencing SEI (bias = .001, p = .000) were statistically significant. All in all, the results confirmed the expectations of the authors. Therefore, hypothesis 3 is rejected in the study.

Table 2: The mediating effect of EP in the relationship between EE and SEI

Pathways/Effects	Estimates (β)	SE	P	Bootstrap with BCa 95% CI	
				Lower Limit	Upper Limit
Total effect					
EE → SEI	.2203	.0309	.0000	.1595	.2811
Direct effect					
EE → EP	.1657	.0282	.0000	.1101	.2213
Indirect effect					
EE → SEI	.1750	.0320	.0000	.1119	.2381
EP → SEI	.2733	.0682	.0001	.1389	.4078

EE → EP → SEI .0453 .0137 Sig .0212 .0744

Note: EE – Entrepreneurship Education; EP – Entrepreneurial Passion; SEI – Social Entrepreneurial Intention; AdjR² – Adjusted R-squared

Source: Researchers' Fieldwork, 2024

The data in Table 2 reveals that the total effect of EE on SEI ($\beta = 0.2203$, $SE = 0.0309$; $p = 0.000$, 95% CI = [0.1595-0.2811]). Also, Table 2 reveals that the direct effect of EE on EP ($\beta = 0.1657$, $SE = 0.0282$; $p = 0.000$, 95% CI = [0.1101-0.2213]) were statistically significant. Table 2 also reveals that the indirect effect of EE on SEI via EP ($\beta = 0.0453$, $SE = 0.0137$; $p < 0.05$, 95% CI = [0.0212-0.0744]) were statistically significant. However, since the direct effect of EE on SEI ($\beta = 0.1750$, $SE = 0.0320$; $p = 0.000$, 95% CI = [0.1119-0.2381]) is statistically significant; the direct effect of EE on EP ($\beta = 0.1657$, $SE = 0.0282$; $p = 0.000$, 95% CI = [0.1101-0.2213]) is statistically significant; and the direct effect of EP on SEI ($\beta = 0.2733$, $SE = 0.0682$; $p = 0.000$, 95% CI = [0.1389-0.4078]) is statistically significant, EP is regarded as a partial mediator in the relationship. Therefore, hypothesis 4 is rejected in the study.

Discussion of Findings

According to hypothesis one analysis, entrepreneurship education is a significant predictor of social entrepreneurial intention. It argues that exposing students to the EE material will encourage them to engage in social entrepreneurship, which will then help to solve societal problems. The discovery supports the findings by Mair and Noboa (2006), Hassan (2020), Ndou (2021) Naweed et al (2021), Chang et al (2021) and Ediagbonya (2022a) who in their various studies found that EE significantly influence social entrepreneurial intention.

The second hypothesis was investigated, and it was found that in Edo State, business education students' entrepreneurial passion is significantly predicted by entrepreneurship education. This means that when the EE program in tertiary institutions is properly implemented, there is likelihood that the program's recipients will be more passionate and excited about starting social entrepreneurship that will help to counteract the rising high unemployment rates and social vices. This finding supports the conclusions made by Arshad et al (2018), and Cai et al, (2021)

According to analysis of hypothesis three, students in business education in Edo State's intention to engage in social entrepreneurship is significantly predicted by their entrepreneurial passion. That is to say, a person's desire to be their own boss might inspire them to start businesses that not only provide them with cash rewards but also aid in resolving some of the social ills and problems that exist. This finding supports the conclusions made by Fard et al (2018) and Zakari et al (2022), Aloulou et al (2023), Chandra et al (2023) and Ediagbonya (2023a) who revealed that entrepreneurial passion is a significant predictor of social entrepreneurial intention. The results of hypothesis four have once more demonstrated that entrepreneurial passion does considerably mediate the association between entrepreneurship education and business education students' social entrepreneurial intention in Edo State.

Conclusion

According to the findings, entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial passion both influence business education students' social entrepreneurial intention in Edo State. It was also determined that in Edo State, entrepreneurial passion significantly mediates the relationship between entrepreneurship education and business education students' social entrepreneurial intention. The findings imply that those charged with teaching social entrepreneurship or entrepreneurship-related courses should make a concerted effort to expose students to the fundamentals of business formation by equipping learners with the desired competencies, which will in turn boost their entrepreneurial passion and influence them in launching a business. This study has made a substantial contribution to knowledge by addressing an empirical and literature gap in this field.

Recommendation

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are therefore put forward:

- i. The practical component of the social entrepreneurship education program be stressed in order to encourage people to start their own businesses aimed at solving societal problems;
- ii. There is an urgent need for curriculum revision in higher education institutions to emphasize social entrepreneurship;
- iii. Social entrepreneurial teachers should be encouraged to plan their teaching programme to make learners more passionate about business formation; and
- iv. Researchers should be encouraged to conduct more studies in the area of social entrepreneurship with a view to addressing gap especially in developing countries.

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